

Title: Telemicrosurgery: robotic assisted microsurgery

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INTRODUCTION:

Microsurgery, developed in the 1960s from experimental work in animals, has not undergone technological evolution until today.

AIM:

Robotics could lead to a major technological leap for two main reasons, the reduction of the size of the incisions thanks to the endoscopy and the improvement of the surgical act by the reduction of the movements.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Robot-assisted microsurgery is of interest in the two major applications of microsurgery, vascular microsurgery and peripheral nerve microsurgery.

RESULTS:

A clinical case of robot-assisted transfer of intercostal nerves to the motor branch of the musculocutaneous nerve for the biceps muscle via intrathoracic minimally invasive approach is presented here. The procedure is performed in two stages, the first in lateral decubitus to take the intercostal nerves, and the second in supine position to carry out the nerve transfer.

CONCLUSIONS:

The advantage of robotics in microsurgery is the increased ergonomics for the surgeon and the reduction of scars for the patient.

KEYWORDS:

Microsurgery; Robotic Microsurgery; Telemicrosurgery

BIOGRAPHY:

Philippe Liverneaux has completed his PhD at the age of 45 years from Paris University and postdoctoral studies from Strasbourg University, France. He is the director of Hand and Microsurgery Department, Strasbourg, France. He has published more than 175 papers in reputed journals and has been serving as an editorial board member of reputed journals. He is member of the board of the European Wrist Arthroscopy Society, past President of the French Society for Microsurgery, past President of the Robotic Assisted & Endoscopic Surgery Society and elected President of the French Society for Surgery of the Hand